

Abstract**Human Papilloma Virus Vaccination in Northern Bauchi: Evaluating Uptake, Completion and Dropout Rates.**

Musa Zakka^{1*}, Sunday E. Achanya², Hassan T. Olayinka², Emmanuel O. Agbogo², Dauda A. Katagum², Bala M. Audu²

Author Affiliations

¹Department of Community Medicine and Public Health, Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital and Federal University of Health Sciences, Azare, Bauchi State, Nigeria.

²Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital and Federal University of Health Sciences, Azare, Bauchi State, Nigeria.

***Correspondence author:** Zakka Musa
Department of Community Medicine and Public Health, Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital and Federal University of Health Sciences, Azare, Bauchi State, Nigeria. **E-mail:** musa.zakka@fuhsa.edu.ng **Tel:** +2348135721640

Background: Cervical cancer is a preventable and curable disease, through universal and equitable access to Human papilloma virus (HPV) vaccination, efficiently coordinated cervical cancer screening, timely diagnosis, quality treatment and palliative care in line with 90-70-90 global targets by 2030. Primary prevention is achieved by HPV immunisation of girls aged 9-14 years. This study aimed to evaluate HPV vaccine uptake, completion and drop-out rates among adolescent girls in Bauchi North.

Materials and Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted in May to July 2025. A

multistage sampling technique was used to select two LGAs from Bauchi North and 23 primary healthcare centres (PHCs) providing HPV vaccination, with simple random sampling by balloting. Data were extracted from PHC immunisation records using a checklist. The study included a target population of 36,061 girls aged 9-14 years. The study analysed the uptake and dropout rates, as well as associated factors, using SPSS version 24.

Results: The HPV vaccine (cervarix) uptake was 3.2%, with 1,163 out of 36,061 girls receiving the first dose. The completion rate for the two doses was 46.7%, with 542 out of 1,163 girls receiving the second dose, while the drop-out rate was 53.3%, with 621 girls not receiving the second dose. Factors significantly associated with vaccine drop-out included lack of awareness (63.5%), fear of infertility (56%), age aggregations (9-14years) (43%), and political misconception (41%).

Conclusion: Low HPV vaccine uptake and high drop-out rates require targeted interventions, including awareness campaigns and community engagement, to improve vaccine uptake and completion.

Keywords: Human papilloma Virus, Vaccine, Uptake, Dropout rate

Open Access article distribution in the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC by 4.0) Copyright: The Author(s). 2025

ISSN: Print; 2992-555X Electronic: 3092-9865
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18910403>

Date Submitted: 20th November 2025

Date Accepted: 2nd March 2026

Date Published Online: 10th March 2026

Cite this article as: Musa Zakka^{1*}, Sunday E. Achanya², Hassan T. Olayinka², Emmanuel O. Agbogo², Dauda A. Katagum², Bala M. Audu² Human Papilloma Virus Vaccination in Northern Bauchi: Evaluating Uptake, Completion and Dropout Rates. *The Scholar J Health Scie* 2026; S2-10